

EDU TRACKS

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**PRIMARY SCHOOLCHILDREN
SCIENTIFIC ENQUIRY**

**UNIVERSITY TEACHERS
IMMEDIACY BEHAVIOUR**

QUALITY EDUCATION

ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS

**HIGHER EDUCATION
QUALITY ASSURANCE**

**EVALUATION OF
ENVIRONMENTAL TEXTBOOKS**

**LANGUAGE TEACHING
MULTILINGUAL APPROACH**

GRADING IN SCHOOLS

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**KALAM'S REFLECTIONS
ON EDUCATION**

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EDUTRACKS

An Evaluation of Environmental Science II Textbooks of Third and Fourth Standards of Andhra Pradesh

Research

The investigators have attempted to evaluate Environmental Science II (EVS II) textbook with the help of specially constructed rating scale. In this rating scale the areas covered include organization of matter, contents of textbooks, accuracy of text material, indications of teaching aids, illustrations used, psychological soundness, and learning activities. The investigators contacted 50 teachers of Andhra Pradesh who were teaching EVS II of third and fourth standard. The data obtained from the respondents were subjected to percentage analysis. The results show that the textbooks have properly organized content, which is presented well; the subject matter has accurate information and the situations and illustrations used belong to rural and urban background. The textbook has helped the teachers in deciding about the teaching aids, the illustrations given are appropriate, the matter presented is psychological sound and appropriate learning activities are presented.

UNESCO (1988) has identified the following objectives of teaching Environmental Education at school level.

- To make the child aware of his Environment in a very simple manner and his/her place in it.
- To arouse interest in the people around him/her and develop understanding of the environment.
- To develop skills for learning about environment i.e. Observation, Collection and Classification.
- To develop willingness to work individually and in groups to maintain and preserve environment, and
- To foster development and positive attitude in pupils towards environment.

Review of Related Literature

Fifteen studies (17% of researches carried out in 5 surveys) in the areas of Social Science pertained to textbook and Instructional material.

Researches in the areas of textbooks in Social Science Education had restricted objectives, scope and methodology. Such studies have been mostly conducted

to evaluate Social Science textbooks in terms of their promoting or hindering national integration (NCERT 1970, P.I.A. 1982); Kher S.N. 1972, Basu, B. and Rao V.K. 1979; Chavan, C.V. (1990). One finds an occasional study such as that of Gagneja (1974) in which an attempt has been made to find out the treatment given to various foreign countries such as the USA, the UK, the USSR, Japan etc., in Social Science textbooks. Another study, which deviates from the routine topics is that of Patyal, C.B. (1977) who tried to study the readability indices of geographical material and its effectiveness in terms of reading comprehension.

Radhamony, P. (1988) carried out an interesting study on textbooks written in Malayalam, using lexical morphemic and syntactic analysis and thus assessed the relevance of this technique for the improvement of Science education. In a rare study Radhamonyamma (1980) evolved an effective model for presentation of chemical ideas through the regional language "Malayalam" in Kerala.

Joshi, P.K. (Ganguli, D. and Vashistha, U.C. 1991) had developed an 'edit' code for evaluation of textbooks.

Most of these studies have been done at least as long as a decade back.

However, in these studies investigators did not come across any study on Urdu textbooks. Hence, the investigators made an effort to study Environmental Science II textbooks of Andhra Pradesh.

Objectives of the Study

The investigators have made an effort to study the textbook with the following objectives.

- To study the organization of matter in EVS II textbooks.
- To study the mode of presentation of contents of the textbooks.
- To study accuracy of presentation of matter.
- To study the adaptability of material to different localities.
- To study the effectiveness of teaching aids.
- To study the appropriateness of illustrations.
- To study the psychological soundness of presentation.

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- To study the aptness of learning activities.

Methodology

The methodology used for the study is given below

Sample

50 teachers teaching EVS II in Hyderabad were drawn by purposive sampling technique.

Tools

Rating Scale

The investigators prepared a rating scale consisting of 8 major areas and a total of 24 items in consultation with teachers, educationists and researchers.

Procedure

The investigator contacted 50 teachers teaching EVS II in Third and Fourth Standard. They were supplied the rating scale and were briefed about the method of answering. The filled in response sheets were collected from them after a gap of one week.

Results and Discussion

The investigators had classified data into two major parts. Part A was to be filled by the respondents. Part B consisted of rating items divided into eight broad areas viz., Organization, Content, Accuracy, Adaptability, Teaching Aids, Illustrations, Psychological Soundness, and Learning Activities. Hence, the investigators have discussed the results in these broader areas.

Part A

Third standard textbook titled Environmental Science II is published by the Government of Andhra Pradesh in 2005. This

Textbook Title	Standard	Publisher	Year of Publication	Text book topics	EVS topics	Pollution topics	Type	Field Visits
E.V.S. II	Third	Government of Andhra Pradesh, Hyderabad	2005	10	10	1	Both	9
E.V.S. II	Fourth	Government of Andhra Pradesh, Hyderabad	2005	11	11	1	Both	14

textbook has 10 topics pertaining to Environmental Science. This textbook has a topic pertaining to environmental pollution, which deals with both urban and rural pollution. The textbook provides opportunity for field visits and the number of visits indicated is 9.

The fourth standard textbook, also titled Environmental Science II, too is published by Government of Andhra Pradesh, in 2005. This textbook has eleven topics and all of these deal with Environmental Science. This textbook has a topic pertaining to environmental pollution that mentions urban and rural pollution. The textbook provides an opportunity for field visit and 14 such situations are indicated.

Part B

Organization

Rating	ItemO1	ItemO2	ItemO3	ItemO4
SA	34.69	18.37	14.29	8.16
A	65.31	67.35	44.90	55.10
U	0.00	14.29	34.69	32.65
D	0.00	0.00	6.12	4.08
SD	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemO1: While most of the respondents (65%) agree that the textbook has a central theme, which relates to the Environmental Science, the other respondents (35%)

strongly agree with this statement.

ItemO2: Most of the respondents (67%) agree that EVS II textbook has areas of interest. Around 18% of respondents strongly agree with this aspect whereas 14% do not have any opinion on this.

ItemO3: In response to the probability of use of the matter in daily life 14% strongly agree with its usage, 45% agree and 35% are undecided about its usage.

ItemO4: In response to the organization of the material, majority of them (55% agree and 8% strongly agree) were of the opinion that the format of presentation is informal and interesting. At the same time 33% are undecided.

Content

Rating	ItemC1	ItemC2	ItemC3	ItemC4
SA	4.08	2.04	8.16	2.04
A	75.51	81.63	67.35	46.94
U	16.33	16.33	22.45	48.98
D	4.08	0.00	2.04	2.04
SD	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemC1: 76% of the respondents agree that the textbooks use inductive approach and 4% of them strongly agree with this, whereas 16% are undecided.

ItemC2: In response to the provision of activity aspect in Environment Science textbooks almost 82% agree with this whereas 16% are undecided.

ItemC3: In the textbooks the new content points (concepts) are introduced in italic and boldface and this feature is supported by 75% of the respondents; 22% who do

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support this feature.

ItemC4: The new content points (concepts) introduced are appropriate as indicated by the majority (2% strongly agree whereas 47% merely agree); there is a large group of 47%, which is undecided on this aspect.

Accuracy

Rating	ItemA1	ItemA2	ItemA3
SA	10.20	18.37	24.49
A	89.80	61.22	65.31
U	0.00	20.41	10.20
D	0.00	0.00	0.00
SD	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemA1: Almost all the respondents either strongly agree (10%) or agree (90%) with the fact that the environmental concepts mentioned in the textbook are scientifically correct.

ItemA2: Majority (18% strongly and 61% merely) agrees that the textbooks avoid personification. About 20% of the respondents do not have any opinion on this.

ItemA3: While 25% of the respondents strongly agree that the textbooks do not have any ambiguity, 65% also agree with this; a small portion of 10% are undecided on this.

Adaptability

Rating	ItemD1	ItemD2
SA	14.29	2.04
A	67.35	46.94
U	18.37	48.98
D	0.00	2.04
SD	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00

ItemD1: In response to the environmental aspect of rural and city background 14% strongly agree, 67% agree and 18% are undecided on the presence of this aspect.

ItemD2: Majority of the respondents (49%) is not sure whether the author gives moral judgment on the controversial environmental issues and human progress. The other larger group of respondents (47%) agrees that the authors give moral judgments too.

Teaching Aids

Rating	ItemT1	ItemT2	ItemT3	ItemT4
SA	0.00	10.20	8.16	10.20
A	51.02	75.51	85.71	55.10
U	32.65	14.29	6.12	34.69
D	12.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
SD	4.08	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemT1: The majority (51%) of respondents agree that the figures and diagrams given in the textbooks are attractive and useful. Thirty three percent are undecided and 16% either disagree or strongly disagree on the usefulness of the figures.

ItemT2: The teachers' manual/handbook is a supplementary tool for teaching as strongly agreed by 10% and agreed by 76% of responded.

ItemT3: The textbook based radio programme is supplementary to the

classroom teaching in the opinion of 86% of the respondents who show their agreement with the statement.

ItemT4: The radio programme 'vindam nerchkundam' is not understood by the students; 55% agree with this, while 35% are undecided.

Illustration

Rating	ItemI1	ItemI2	ItemI3
SA	0.00	0.00	0.00
A	81.63	44.90	28.57
U	14.29	44.90	57.14
D	4.08	8.16	8.16
SD	0.00	2.04	6.12
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemI1: Majority of the respondents (around 82%) agrees that the illustrations used in the textbook are relatively modern.

ItemI2: There is equal response for clarity of figures given in the textbooks. An equal number of respondents (about 45%) agree with the clarity of figures while the same number of respondents is undecided on this issue.

ItemI3: In response to the labeling of the figures the majority (57%) appears to be undecided on the appropriateness of the labeling of figures.

Psychological Soundness

Rating	ItemP1	ItemP2
SA	4.08	10.20
A	85.71	75.51
U	10.20	14.29
D	0.00	0.00
SD	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00

ItemP1: Majority (86%) of the respondents agrees that the text material motivates students by taking them from known to unknown.

ItemP2: Majority of the respondents (76%) agrees that the textbooks provide a lot exercises.

Learning Activities

Rating	ItemL1	ItemL2	ItemL3
SA	8.16	6.12	6.12
A	77.55	75.51	93.88
U	14.29	16.33	0.00
D	0.00	2.04	0.00
SD	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

ItemL1: In response to the number of activities provided in the textbooks, about 78% agree that these are sufficient in number.

ItemL2: Majority of the respondents (76%) agrees that these activities can be performed by utilizing locally available resources.

ItemL3: The activities provided were relevant to the context in the opinion of 94% of the respondents who agree with this.

Summary

Findings

– Most of the teachers agree that the content of the text is organized properly.

- Most of the respondents agree that the presentation of content in the textbook is good.
- Most of the respondents agree that the matter presented in textbooks is accurate.
- Most of the respondents feel that the textbook has material pertaining to both rural and urban background.
- Most of the respondents agree that the textbook indicates appropriate teaching aids.
- Most of the respondents agree with the illustrations given in the textbook.
- Most of the respondents agree that the material presented in the text is psychologically sound.
- Most of the respondents agree that the learning activities presented in the text is appropriate.

Limitations

- i) The study is limited to textbooks of third and fourth standards only.
- ii) The investigators have restricted their study to only EVS II subject.
- iii) This investigation is restricted to only a small sample located in Andhra Pradesh.
- iv) Purposive selected 50 teachers comprise the sample.
- v) The majority of the respondents are Urdu medium teachers; hence, not a representative sample of the state.

Suggestions

- i) The study can be done on the representative sample of the state.
- ii) The study may also be conducted in other branches of academic subjects.
- iii) Observation, Classification, Measurements, Counting, Communication, Questioning, and Investigation are very important skills in

environmental study and the textbook should be studied *vis-à-vis* development of these skills in children.

Educational Implications

- a) The textbook has strong psychological foundations
- b) It is pleasant to note that the textbooks are based on activities and make use of locally available material.
- c) The textbook should have more environmental matter, which can be of use in everyday life.
- d) The publishers can attempt an informal and interesting way of presentation of the Self-instructional Material (SIM).
- e) About half of the respondents are undecided about introduction of new concepts based on the maturity level of the students. Hence, a serious thought has to be given to the maturity level of the students and introduction of the new topics.
- f) The respondents restrained themselves from giving their opinion on whether the authors extend moral judgment on controversial environmental subjects and human progress. There are many occasions when pollution occurs due to the unplanned livelihood. Hence, this aspect should be highlighted.
- g) The figures and diagrams given in the textbooks can be made much more attractive and useful.
- h) A huge number of respondents do not have any opinion regarding radio programme 'Vindam Nerchkunam'. Hence, this programme can be made more popular. Also an effort can be made to bring out programmes for Urdu schools in their native language.●